

Analysis of the Cropping Pattern in Dhule District (M.S.).

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Abstract:

New cropping patterns have been accepted by the farmers of the study region, due to climate change and uneven rainfall. Geographical and economical factors have boosted the cultivation and production of cereals crop. The Dhule district is drought prone district, so it is selected for present study. Agriculture is the main occupation in the district, geographical phenomena is uneven. Annual rainfall is unsatisfied for agriculture. Therefore, the study of spatial distribution and temporal variability were vital in characterizing the geographic factor and nature of cereals crop cultivation. Therefore it is important to study the cropping pattern in this district. The aim of present paper is to examine the temporal changes and relation between rainfall and cropping pattern. Present study is based on secondary source of data year 2005 and 2015. Simple statistical technique is used to analyze the changing trend of cropping pattern. For calculating transformation the data 2005 and 2015 are compared. The data is representing with graph and map using GIS software and MS Excel is applied to analyze. In Dhule district area under cereals crops are changes in various tehasils. Cereals crops cultivation has occupied area 247051 Ha. (60.26% of NSA) in the year 2005 and occupied area decrease upto 145056 Ha. (37.16 % of NSA) in the year 2009 due to the flexibility of the rainfall. Keyword: Crop, Cropping pattern, Drought prone, Plantation, Agriculture

Introduction:

India has a great diverse agricultural systems as well as it possesses rich agricultural resources, different geographical factors had resulted into agricultural typologies. Therefore, important agricultural facility is useful programme to improved productivity and thereby achieving rural development. They may be achieved by technological intervention and by adopting strategic cropping pattern. This would reduce the water requirement of agricultural without comprising agricultural output. Maharashtra is leading

state in area and production of cereals crops in the country. According to some expert and farmers there is a shift from cereals crops to other because of water requirement, low input and high profitability over these crops. Drought is a major problem in Dhule district. They are natural hazards and are related with rainfall. Drought may be best benefited as persistent and abnormal moisture deficiency that has an adverse impact on agriculture. Agriculture in this district is mostly of intensive subsistence type. There are two main crop growing seasons, its Kharif and Rabbi. Jawar crop is grown in both seasons.

Study area: The shape of the study area is triangular. It is located in the northern part of the Maharashtra State. It has occupied over an area of 8063.11 sq.km. It is extended from 20⁰38 N to 21⁰39 N latitudes and from 73⁰50 E to 75⁰13¹ E longitudes (Fig. No.1). Dhule district contributes 2.62 percent total geographical area of the Maharashtra State. As per the 2011 Census, the population of Dhule district is 2,048, 781. The density of population is 285 persons per sq. km.

LOCATION MAP

Objectives:

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To study the temporal changing cropping pattern of Dhule district.

To study the relation between rainfall and cropping pattern of Dhule district.

Hypothesis:

Cereals cropping pattern depend on rainy days and annual rainfall

Database and Methodology:

In this study secondary data have been collected from various socio-economic reports of Dhule districts. Analysis the 2005 and 2015 is cropping pattern. Simple statistical techniques are used to analyze the changing trend in cropping pattern, for calculating transformation the data 2005 and 2009 are compared. The data have been summarized processed and represented with graph and map using GIS software, MS Excel was applied to process and analysis the data. In the present paper out of all crops only cereal cropping pattern has been studied. Cereal crops like Bajara, Rice, Wheat, Maize, Jower, Nachani and Pulses are studied.

Results and Discussion:

Dhule district comes under drought prone area. Cereal crop is a major crop in this district. Tahsilwise rainfall is varied; hence cereals crop cultivation is also uneven. Annual rain fall is highest in Shirpur tahsil (above 700mm). Shirpur tahsil does not come under drought area. Therefore amount of cereal crop is 43% of NSA in 2005 and 15% of NSA in 2015. Shindkhed Dhule and eastern part of Sakri tahsil come under drought prone area. Hence near about 70% of NSA fall under cultivation area of cereal crops. In 2015 due to rainfall is increase cereal crop cultivation area has been declined from 60% of NSA (2005) to 37% of NSA (2015). Sakri tahsil stood first in cereal crop cultivation in Dhule district (70% of NSA 2005 and 51% of NSA in 2015) Bajara crop cultivated all over the district, area under Bajara crop in 2005 was 60.26% of NSA and in 2015 it was 37.16%. In 2015 due to increase in rainfall (Annual average rainfall 673mm) instead of cereal cropping pattern other cash crop cultivated area has been increased.

The net sown area in the Dhue district was 409900ha. and 390458ha. year 2005 and 2015 respectively. This year cereals have occupied 247051ha. (60.26% of NSA) and 145096ha. (37.16% of NSA) area in 2005 and 2015 respectively. The main cereals crops have been Bajara, Jawar and Wheat are the important food grain crop in the district. Maize is mostly grown in the irrigated areas. High proportion of cereals indicated that the tahasils has very low level of commercialization of agriculture. The field observation revealed that the tahsils dominated by cereals with slightly more than half the cultivated areas.

Bajara :

Bajara is the important food crop cultivated in the district. It is generally taken in kharif season and hence it must have replaced hybrid that was grown in the same season. It is usually grown on the light to medium soil. It requires dry climate and less rainfall bajara is grown everywhere in the district. The use of high yielding varieties of seeds is increased in the district. The farmer mostly areas this crop when the amount of rainfall is less. Through bajara is the important kharif crop it is also grown in rabbi season Dhule and Shindkheda tahasils. Rabbi bajara is grown in the summer season in the villages having the irrigation facilities. Climate of the district is suitable for Bajara crop. This crop can be taken low amount of rainfall. Sakri tahsil stood first in the cultivation area of bajara 33.51 % of NSA, it is follow by Dhule (30.59% of NSA), Shindkheda (24.46% of NSA) and lowest area under cultivation is Shirpur tahsil which is 15.22% of NSA in 2005. In 2015, due to increase in rainfall, inspite of bajara, maize and other cash crops have been cultivated.

Jowar:

Jowar is also important food grain crop in the district. It is cultivated in kharif and rabbi crop season. The jowar cultivation is basically related to firstly low rainfall and secondly soil in the district. It is traditionally cultivated as a rain feed crop in the both seasons. Jowar is cultivated all over the district. Highest area under cultivation of jowar is in dhule tahsil (19.68% of NSA), which is followed by Shindkheda (15.12% of NSA), Shirpur (10.55% of NSA) and lowest area under jowar cultivation is in Sakri tahsil (1.26% of NSA) in 2005. But in 2015, due to increase in average rainfall, area under this crop has been declined.

Rice:

Rice crop is cultivated only in western part of Sakri tahsil and Shirpur tahsil in Dhule district. The average annual rainfall in this area is 650 to 750mm, which is higher and suitable for rice crop. The area under cultivation is increased Sakri tahsil 3.72% of NSA in 2005 to 10.54% of NSA in 2015. Dhule tahsil this crop is rarely cultivation and in Shindkheda tahsil rice crop is not cultivated.

Tehsil	Sr. No.	Crops	2005			2015		
			Area in Ha.	% of NSA	% of Cereals	Area in Ha.	% of NSA	% of Cereals
Shirpur	1	Bajara	9242	15.22	21.598	3404	5.35	16.52
	2	Jawar	6408	10.55	14.975	2181	3.43	10.59
	3	Rice	20	0.03	0.047	0	0	0
	4	Wheat	653	1.08	1.526	1456	2.29	7.07
	5	Maize	0	0.00	0.000	118	0.19	0.57
	6	Nachni	0	0.00	0.000	0	0.00	0.00
	8	Pulses	10165	16.74	23.755	6286	9.89	30.51
	Total		26488	43.61	61.901	13445	21.15	65.25
Shindkheda	1	Bajara	26038	24.46	25.63	19283	20.07	28.82
	2	Jawar	16094	15.12	15.84	6058	6.30	9.06
	3	Rice	0	0.00	0.00	0	0.00	0
	4	Wheat	810	0.76	0.80	1370	1.43	2.05
	5	Maize	277	0.26	0.27	523	0.54	0.78
	6	Nachni	0	0.00	0.00	0	0.00	0.00
	8	Pulses	15145	14.23	14.91	13431	13.98	20.08
	Total		58364	54.83	57.45	40665	42.32	60.79
Sakri	1	Bajara	48662	35.51	27.28	1942	1.65	1.09
	2	Jawar	1731	1.26	0.97	4	0.00	0.00

	3	Rice	5103	3.72	2.86	12422	10.54	11.65
	4	Wheat	3425	2.50	1.92	6164	5.23	3.46
	5	Maize	13463	9.82	7.55	22369	18.99	12.54
	6	Nachni	4399	3.21	2.47	921	0.78	0.52
	8	Pulses	19007	13.87	10.66	17049	14.47	9.56
	Total		95790	69.89	53.71	60871	51.67	38.82
Dhule	1	Bajara	32318	30.59	25.99	3112	2.76	5.07
	2	Jawar	20796	19.68	16.72	12926	11.44	21.06
	3	Rice	2	0.00	0.00	14	0.01	0.02
	4	Wheat	2052	1.94	1.65	2332	2.06	3.80
	5	Maize	2770	2.62	2.23	3201	2.83	5.21
	6	Nachni	0	0.00	0.00	0	0.00	0.00
	8	Pulses	8471	8.02	6.81	8530	7.55	13.90
	Total		66409	62.85	53.41	30115	26.66	49.06
Total			247051	60.26		145096	37.16	
Source: Dhule district Socio-Economic Report, 2005 &2015								

Table no: Tehsil wise Annual rainfall, Raini days and Drought prone Villages in Dhule district. (2005 and 2009)

Sr. No.	Tehsils	Annual Rainfall in mm				Total Villages	Drought prone Villages	NSA in Ha.	
		2005	Rain i days	2015	Raini days			2005	2009
1	Shirpur	603	47	687	23	152	0	60732	63569
2	Shindkhe da	388	41	584	26	143	143	106446	96100

3	Sakri	687	44	774	32	212	110	137056	11780 4
4	Dhule	318	40	623	28	166	166	105666	11298 5
Average/Total		499	172	667	109	673	419	409900	39045 8
Rainfall in %		92		110					
Source: Agriculture Commissioner Office, Pune									

Wheat:

Wheat is the third important food grain in the district. This crop is grown in the medium and black soil. It is cultivated in dry and cool month of rabbi season. The farmer has grown the crop on a very small scale in the district. The crop is taken as an irrigated crop. The agricultural land is prepared after the harvested season of bajara. Sowing is done in the month of Oct. / Nov. The crop date takes 110 to 140 days to mature from the date of sowing. Now, improved varieties of seed are sown in the district. Wheat cultivation area increased the mainly because of increase in area under irrigation by Panzar, Kan and Kabryakhadak medium projects. This crop is cultivated very less (1 to 3.8% of NSA) Dhule district in 2015. Climate of the District is not suitable for this crop. Therefore, the average production of this crop is very less.

Maize:

Maize is important crop which is mostly used as a fodder in the Sakri, Dhule and Shindakheda tahsils. The area under maize has increased for the year 2005 (4.23 of % NSA) to the year 2009 (5.63% of NSA). Maize crop gives a higher production and income of the farmer in Dhule district. The area under cultivation of this crop is increasing day by day. The climate of this District except Shirpur tahsil, is favorable for this crop. In 2005 highest area under cultivation of the crop is Sakri (9.82% of NSA) and it followed by Dhule (2.62% of NSA), Shindkheda (0.26% of NSA). The crop requires water in large amount. It needs irrigation facility. In Sakri tahsil Panzara, Kan, Kamkheli and Kabryakhadak

irrigation medium water tank. Whereas, in 2015, the area under cultivation of the crop is increased double higher due to hybrid seed and irrigation facilities.

Nachni:

Nachni is important kharif crop in only Sakri tahsil in Dhule district. The area under Nachani in year 2005 was 3.21 % of NSA and year 2015 was 0.75% of NSA in Sakri tahsil. The Nachani is grown on the light soil and heavy rainfall area. In high rainfall area, this crop is cultivation. In Dhule district, only in western part of Sakri tahsil Nachani crop is cultivated, which is due to the high rainfall in hilly area of Sayadri. The crop is cultivated in (3.21% of NSA) area as per 2005.

Pulses:

Pulses grown in all tahsils in Dhule district. It is dominant crop in shirpur tahsil. It is account 13.21% of NSA in year 2005 and 11.47% of NSA in year 2015. In the tahsil a variety of pulses area grown like Gram, Tur, Green gram, Mug, Chavali, Wal, Green peas etc. Almost all the pulses except Gram and Tur are cultivated in kharif season. Mostly varieties of pulses are cultivated in all tahsils in dhule district. The pulses are grown on light soil in the district. This crop can be cultivated in both less and high rainfall area. This crop is economically beneficial. The crop is cultivated in all tehils of the district. In 2015 in Sakri tahsil, the crop is cultivated in 14.17% of NSA.

Generally, cereal crop is cultivated all over the district. If rainfall is increased, other crops like cotton, Sugarcane Vegetable can be cultivated in large amount. Dhule district is drought prone area, hence cereals cropping pattern analysis is essential. Geographical and technological factors affect on the cereals cropping pattern.

Suggestions:

1. For cereals crop, instead of traditional cropping pattern, new technological cropping needs to be accepted for better results.
2. Newly developed hybrid seeds of cereals crop need to be used.
3. Where there is less rainfall, irrigation system based on new technology is to be used.
4. In less rainfall and less area, higher productivity cropping pattern to be accepted.
5. Fruit crop cultivated in less water area like Pomegranate, Crusted Apple, Ber etc. are to cultivated

6. Cereal crops should be taken for commercial purposes instead of traditional cropping pattern.

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